

ethanol, cyclohexanol, chlorobenzene and nitrobenzene have been worked out from cryoscopic measurements. All the polar liquids are found to be unassociated in DMSO showing a strong dipole-dipole interaction in solution. It seems therefore, very interesting to see how nonpolar liquids behave in DMSO because question of dipole-dipole interaction does not arise in case of nonpolar liquids. Some nonpolar liquids namely benzene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and cyclohexane are chosen for the present studies, and osmotic coefficient and the activity of solvent (DMSO) is determined in solutions of these liquids from cryoscopic measurements.

Experimental

DMSO (Fluka, purum grade) and all other liquids were used after purification in the manner described earlier².

The simple Beckman apparatus was used for measuring depression in freezing point (ΔT) in solutions. The rest of the procedure for measuring depression in freezing point and calculating apparent molecular weight of solute and osmotic coefficient and activity of solvent was as given in our previous studies¹.

Results and Discussion

The values of apparent molecular weight of solute, osmotic coefficient ' ϕ ' and activity 'a' of solvent (DMSO) in different systems at different concentrations are given in Table 1.

It may be noted from Table 1 that all the solutes have nearly normal molecular weights in DMSO. Since the solutions used are not very dilute, hence there is erratic change in the apparent molecular weight of the solutes.

Osmotic coefficients in all systems are nearly unity at higher concentrations. This shows the absence of self molecular association of these organic liquids in DMSO; also these systems do not appear to show any deviations from Raoult's law. It indicates an appreciable dipole-induced dipole interaction between solute and solvent molecules which causes the solute molecules to remain unassociated.

The activity of the solvent in different solutions decreases as the concentration of the solute in the solution increases. From the activity (a) data given in Table 1, 'a' vs m curves were drawn. Same type of straight line is observed in all cases. On extrapolating the straight lines to zero concentration, activity of solvent is found to be unity in every case, showing that solutions become more ideal in dilute range.

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Chemical Investigation on Some Mangrove Species Part IV. *Heritiera minor*, a typical Mangrove species

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IN continuation of our earlier report¹⁻³ on ecological influence on taxonomic variation, we report herein the chemical investigation of the leaves and barks of *Heritiera minor* (Fam. Sterculiaceae), a typical Mangrove species of Sundarban. It is a small tree with blend root sucker. The plant materials were collected in the month of December. No chemical work appears to have been reported on this genus.

Petroleum extract of the leaves was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction yielded waxy materials, yet to be characterised. The neutral part on column chromatography over silica gel G yielded the following fractions.

The first fraction furnished a solid material (0.25g), m.p. 245°, $C_{30}H_{60}O$ (M^+426). IR absorption at 1715 cm^{-1} , mass fragmentation pattern and NMR signals showed its identity with friedelin; oxime, m.p. 286°.

Second fraction was triacontanol (0.07g), m.p. 82°.

Third fraction which registered intense spot with Rf 0.42 (solvent: chloroform) on repeated recrystallisations from benzene-alcohol yielded two crystalline materials, compounds A (0.70g) and B (3.50g). Compound A had m.p. 268°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$, $M^+ 3400$ (-OH), 1635 and 812 cm^{-1} (double bond); M. S. m/e 426(M^+); acetate, m.p. 300°, and was identified as taraxerol. Compound B, m.p. 195°, isolated from the filtrate of compound A was purified through preparative tlc. Superimposable IR spectrum and co-glc on 3% SE-30 on gas chrome-Z, 60-80 mesh (Ret. time: 17.0 mins at 250° - 52°) showed its identity with β -amyryn.

The last fraction was β -sitosterol, m.p. 138°. The bark of *H. minor* on similar work-up showed the presence of all the constituents of leaves with lower yield in each case.

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Methanolysis of the Anhydride of 1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-Acetic Acid : A Comment.

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IN contradiction to the earlier reports by Khuda and Bhattacharya¹, who depicted the formation of the half-ester-acid (III) by methanolysis of the anhydride (I), Saharia and his co-workers² have recently reported that methanolysis of the anhydride (I) produces the isomeric half-ester-acid (II) as the only product.

- (II) R=CH₃; R'=H
 (III) R=H; R'=CH₃
 (IV) R=R'=C₂H₅
 (V) R=C₂H₅; R'=H
 (VI) R=R'=CH₃

In connection with synthetic studies in resin acids it was reported from this laboratory³ that partial hydrolysis of the diethyl ester (IV) gives the mono acid ester (V). Accordingly, partial hydrolysis (5% methanolic potassium hydroxide—1 hr) of the dimethyl ester (VI), [n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.51 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.50 (br s, 2H, methylene), 3.60 (s, 3H, -CH₂-COOCH₃) and 3.65 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)] prepared from the corresponding diacid^{4,5} by esterification with an excess of ethereal diazomethane, produces the half-acid ester (II) as the major acidic product, m.p. 56° [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.55 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOH), 3.65 (s, 3H, t-COOCH₃) and 10.00 (br s, 1H, COOH, exchangeable with D₂O)]. In the present study the methanolysis of anhydride (I) according to Saharia and his co-workers² afforded a mixture of two half-acid esters (II) and (III) containing Ca 10-15% of (II) as estimated from the integration ratio of the respective methyl ester singlets in the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum. After repeated column chromatography on silica gel using petroleum ether—ether (9:1), eluents furnished the pure half acid ester (III) [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.53 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOCH₃), 3.60 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)

and 10.80 (s, 1H, —C—COOH , exchangeable with D₂O)] as a thick liquid. The present reinvestigation

thus confirms again the general observations⁶ recorded for the opening of substituted succinic anhydrides by treatment with alcohols.

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Chemical Investigation on *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don.

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THE neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the fern *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don on careful chromatography afforded two hydrocarbons together with six alcohols shown in Table 1.

Fernene, flicene, cyclolaudenol and dryocrassol were identified by direct comparison with authentic specimens (m.m.p and Co-IR). The mother liquor from the crystallisation of cyclolaudenol was seen to be a mixture of two compounds one of which was cyclolaudenol (TLC). The mixture of alcohols (A), m.p. 121-22°, on acetylation gave an acetate (B), m.p. 107-108°, (α)_D + 55.17° and on catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Pd-C gave a compound (C), m.p. 132-34°, which on acetylation gave an acetate (D), m.p. 127-28°. NMR spectra of the original mixture (A) and its acetate (B)

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